

COMPULSORY ATTENDANCE AS A TYPE OF PROCEDURAL COERCIVE MEASURE

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During the trial of civil cases by the courts, it is ensured that all the participants in the proceedings comply with the procedural rules established by the Code of Civil Procedure, and they resolve civil cases in a meaningful way. The parties, as well as the participants of the proceedings, must use their rights and obligations set forth in the procedural code in an honest manner for each participant, and this situation serves to prevent excessive time and money consumption in the process of the proceedings, and to increase the efficiency of court work.

A number of scientific-theoretical views and debates are ongoing regarding the need, importance and essence of this institute. In particular, Z.N. Esanova, a distinguished lawyer in Uzbekistan, prof.

- ensures that the persons participating in the case strictly follow the procedural procedures;
- they help the timely and high-quality conduct of court proceedings;
- serves to increase the authority of the institution of procedural coercive measures;
- saves procedural time (time);
- strengthens procedural obligation and discipline in court[1].

In Chapter 14 of the Civil Procedure Code adopted in the new version, mandatory citation in the cases provided for in the Civil Procedure Code as procedural coercion measures; caution; expulsion from the courtroom; it is established that a court fine can be applied.

The main goal in the cases under consideration in the court process is to restore the violated rights of the participants in the process, to ensure justice. Of course, in order to ensure this, the participation of the parties in the court proceedings is considered important. Because, first of all, if one or both of the parties, who have been duly notified about the date and place of the trial, do not appear, the trial will be postponed. This situation, in turn, leads to the extension of the procedural terms and the extension of the protection of the rights of the applicant or the claimant.

Also, in the event that the defendant, duly informed about the time and place of the court session, did not come to the court session, did not report that there were good reasons for his absence, and did not ask to hear the case without his participation, if the plaintiff if he does not object, the case can be considered in absentia. Even if several defendants participated in the case and all the defendants did not appear at the court session, the case may be heard in absentia. The court will issue a decision on how to deal with the case in this manner. Importantly, for the court to consider the case, there should be information in the case that the defendant has been properly informed. In this case, it is possible to protect the rights of the claimant or the applicant by following the procedural period.

However, in accordance with the new edition of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan[2], in cases where it is necessary to participate in the court proceedings or in cases where it is envisaged to appear in court, a person who has been duly notified does not appear in court for no reason or the reasons for not appearing in court are known. If he does not, the court may issue a ruling on compulsory bringing against him. The implementation of this decision is entrusted to the regional internal affairs body. The collection of expenses related to compulsory bringing is carried out in accordance with the established procedure based on the relevant application of the regional internal affairs body. Costs related to compulsory delivery shall be charged to the state for the benefit of the court[3].

The fact that these expenses must be paid by the person brought to the court serves to ensure that the persons participating in the case follow the procedural rules without deviation.

In the experience of foreign countries, according to the German Code of Civil Procedure[4] the parties to the court session convened in the prescribed manner, the costs arising from the non-appearance of witnesses, experts, specialists of the third parties assisting the trial, are charged from these persons. A fine shall be levied, and if this cannot be levied, he shall be sentenced to compulsory imprisonment.

In England, a special "Contempt of court act" aimed at regulating these issues was adopted[5] In paragraph 17 of this act, for contempt of the Court (arrival of the participants in the court session, disobeying the court order or ignoring them; taking photos or shouting in court (disrupting the trial); refusal of the witness to answer the court's questions; (e.g., publicly commenting on a court

case on social networks or news on the Internet, etc.) for violation of the court process, the collection of court costs and the imposition of fines are established. Failure to pay a fine may result in additional fines or deprivation of certain rights or imprisonment.

According to the current legislation, it is established that the expenses incurred for the search of the defendant should be included in the expenses related to the consideration of the court case. According to the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan[6], according to the general rule, it is established that the court costs in the case will be paid by the party who has won the dispute unfairly. This may cause misunderstanding. Therefore, in our opinion, the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The first paragraph of Article 144 should be supplemented with the following: "Costs related to forced deportation shall be charged to the state in court proceedings from the person who is forcibly detained".

Also, in our opinion, the first part of Article 143 of the Civil Procedure Code, paragraph 1, is called "compulsory bringing in the cases provided for by this Code", and separately only in Article 222 of the Criminal Procedure Code "If the summoned witness does not appear at the court session according to the second summons, he taking into account the fact that it can be brought in a compulsory manner according to the court's decision, it is appropriate to name the first paragraph of Article 143 as "Compulsory attendance".

The development of the system of coercive measures in the course of conducting civil court cases allows for timely and objective consideration of cases. Therefore, it is appropriate to improve our legislation based on the experience of the states analyzed above.

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3. Resolution No. 1024 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the approval of the regulation on the procedure for the execution of orders for the compulsory bringing of persons who refuse to appear in court for investigation, preliminary investigation bodies or court for no reason" 15.12.2018

4. Code of Civil Procedure published on 5 December 2005 (Bundesgesetzblatt (BGBl., Federal Law Gazette) p. 3202; 2006 p. 431; 2007 p. 1781), last amended by Article 1 of the Act of 10 October 2013 (Federal Law) newspaper page 3786;
5. Contempt of Court Act 1981
[/https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1981/49](https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1981/49)
6. Resolution No. 14 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the practice of collecting court costs in civil cases" 24.11.2009

